

Pretreatment eliminates throat irritation by water yam and facilitates the development of functional cookies

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Functional water yam cookies

Abstract

Water yam (*Dioscoreaalata*) provides sufficient nutrients in terms of protein (10.075±0.021%), fiber (3.40±0.03%), and minerals (potassium and phosphorous). However, due to the presence of anti-nutritional factors such as saponins, water yam causes throat irritation. Consequentially, it is less preferred among consumers, and thus the commercial importance of yam tubers has been limited. The current investigation aims to reduce the saponin content of water yam by pretreatment of yam tubers at the optimized conditions (blanching with 0.2% potassium metabisulfite, 0.5% tartaric acid, and 0.5% citric acid) that rendered a 50% reduction in the saponin content (1.65% to 0.86%). The said nutritious yam flour was utilized as a replacement of refined wheat flour (13%) in the development of functional cookies. The yam cookies showed higher mineral content (phosphorous: 116.20±0.80 mg/100 g; potassium: 221.11±0.98 mg/100 g). Reduced water activity and incorporation of antioxidants in yam cookies decreased the peroxide value of the same during storage attesting its higher shelf-life.

Keywords: *Saponin; itchiness; blanching; yam flour; sensory evaluation.*

Introduction

Yams (*Dioscorea spp.*) are one of the most common food crops in South East Asia, India, the Caribbean, and South America (Ferraro, Piccirillo, Tomlins, & Pintado, 2016). It is recognized as the fourth most important root and tuber crop after potatoes, cassava, and sweet potatoes. Yam tubers contain important dietary supplements such as protein, well-balanced basic amino acids, polyphenols, dietary fibers, and several dietary minerals (Gwa and Adi 2015; Hsu *et al.* 2003). These tubers also have been found useful in preventive treatment in patients of arthritis, cancer, diabetes, gastrointestinal diseases, high cholesterol, and inflammatory diseases (Yang & Lin, 2008).

Water yam (*Dioscorea alata* L.) is one of the most widely consumed yam species in the list of staple foods. Though water yam is rich in essential minerals including potassium and phosphorous, it has a bitter taste. Yams are also known to cause discomfort and irritation in the oral cavity and throat areas when consumed (Bhandari and Kawabata, 2004; Okwu and Ndu 2006). These limitations have been attributed to alkaloids and saponins in yams (Okwu and Ndu, 2006). Therefore, the reduction of saponin in yams could improve the edibility and bioavailability of functional constituents.

To design a facile technique for the said aim, various pretreatments have been undertaken in this study. The primary objective was to identify the optimized process parameters for reducing the itchiness in yams when consumed. Blanching at high temperature is an effective method known to reduce saponin in tubers (Ezeocha and Ojmelukwe, 2012; Wahab *et al.* 2015). Further, reports also claim that thermal processing treatment reduces anti-nutritional factors and enhances the bioavailability of minerals (Sharma, Singh, Sharma, Kumar, & Yadav, 2018). Lin *et al.* (2006) have observed high reduction in saponin content of Taiwanese yam after frying at 200°C for 10 min, however, this excessive temperature is detrimental for the phytochemical properties of yam. Therefore, in this work, blanching of yam slices was conducted to reduce the bitterness and itchiness. Potassium metabisulfite (0.28%) reportedly reduces the saponin content in different yam varieties (Adebowale *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, 0.2% potassium metabisulfite was used during blanching of yam.

Citric and tartaric acids are widely used antioxidants in the food industry. In a study conducted by Pertiwi, Nurhalimah, and Aminullah (2020), citric acid (0.5%) effectively reduced the anti-nutritional property of ripe canistel fruit flour. Similar work has been reported by Bukhari, AM, and Ahmed (2017), where citric acid reduced the saponin content in argane press cake.

Tartaric acid is another commonly used antioxidant and food preservative agent (Beri *et al.* 2020; Aryal and Liakopoulou-Kyriakides 2020). In the present study, to reduce the saponin content of yam, these three antioxidants were employed along with blanching.

Since yams are starch-rich and have high pasting property, they could be employed for food fortification, such as in bakery products (Suriya *et al.* 2017; Owo *et al.* 2016). Besides, their functional constituents would add value to the product. Suriya *et al.* (2017) has worked on the elephant foot yam powder to replace 70% of wheat flour; Compendio and Galvez (2017) have used bitter yam or *namiflour* along with oxidant and soybean flour to prepare cookie. Similarly, the development of functional cookies with yam flour as a functional replacement/partial replacement of the conventional wheat flour was also envisaged as a secondary objective in this work.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Freshwater yams, refined wheat flour, vegetable fat, sugar, and vanilla essence were procured from the local supermarket in Thanjavur, Tamil Nadu, India. The average moisture content of the yam tubers was estimated to be $68.68 \pm 2.12\%$ (wet basis). All chemicals and reagents required for this study were of AR grade and were procured from Himedia, Mumbai, India.

Pretreatment methods applied to yam

The water yam tubers were cleaned thoroughly with water, peeled, and cut into thin slices. In the current study, the yam slices were blanched following the methods as stated in Table 1 to reduce saponins, and also retain its natural color. From preliminary study, blanching temperature and time were fixed at 80°C for 10 min. The untreated sample was considered as control yam. For each pretreatment, 1 kg of slices was first washed twice with distilled water and then blanched with different combinations of 0.5% citric acid, 0.5% tartaric acid, and 0.2% potassium metabisulphite (Table 1). Post-blanching the yam slices were dried overnight in a tray dryer at 60°C. The dried slices were then subjected to sensory evaluation as described later. The pretreatment that showed a significant reduction of itchiness in the sensory analysis was denoted as the ‘optimized method’ and the slices obtained from the said method were denoted as the ‘treated yam’. The control and treated yam slices were ground, and the powders were passed through a 0.22 mm mesh, packed in aluminum pouches, and kept at room temperature in dark. Characterization of both control and treated yam powders in terms of

proximate analysis, mineral content, water activity, water absorption capacity, oil absorption capacity and color analysis have been elaborated in supplementary file.

Estimation of phytochemical properties of yam flour

Extraction of bioactive compounds

In brief, 0.5 g of yam powder was subjected to methanolic extraction with 10 mL of 80% methanol for 10 min at 60°C. The extract was collected by centrifugation at 3000 g for 15 min and then used for the analysis of total phenolic and saponin contents.

Estimation of total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of yam flour (control and treated) was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method according to the method reported by Dutta and Bhattacharjee (2017) and was expressed as g gallic acid equivalents per g sample (dry basis).

Determination of saponin content

The reduction of saponin content in treated yam with respect to control yam was estimated based on the method reported by Okwu and Ndu (2006). About 20 g of the sample was dispersed in 200 mL of 20% ethanol. The suspension was heated at 55°C in a hot water bath for 4 h with continuous stirring. Then the supernatant was separated, and the residue was retreated. The combined extract was reduced in volume to 40 mL in a water bath at 90°C. The concentrate was transferred to a separating funnel where 20 mL diethyl ether was added to it and shaken vigorously. The aqueous layer was retrieved, while the ether layer was discarded. The resulting solution was heated in a water bath to evaporate the water. Upon evaporation, the sample was dried in a hot air oven and the residual weight was measured to assess the total saponin content.

Preparation of yam flour incorporated cookie

Yam cookies were prepared by replacing refined wheat flour with ‘treated yam powder’ obtained from the ‘optimized condition’. The concentration of yam powder in preparation of cookies was tested at 1%, 5%, 10%, 13%, and 15%. From preliminary trials, it was observed that, beyond 15% of yam powder, the cookies exhibited bitterness and itchiness in the throat. Therefore, the maximum concentration of yam powder in the cookie was fixed at 15%. Control cookies were also prepared with wheat flour only.

For cookie preparation, the method reported by Theagarajan *et al.* (2019) was followed. After baking at 160°C for 12 min in a preheated baking oven (Lab Tech, India), the cookies were cooled and tightly sealed in aluminum pouches and stored under nitrogen at room temperature (23±2°C) in a desiccator for further analyses and storage study. All these cookies were subsequently examined by sensory evaluation to obtain the optimized concentration of yam powder for incorporation into the cookie dough.

Sensory analysis of yam powder and yam cookies

Sensory evaluation was conducted for all the yam slices (control and all pre-treated samples) and cookies (control, 1%, 5%, 10%, 13%, and 15%). For both cases, the semi-trained sensory panel was comprised of 20 members who were research scholars and technical staff of the department representing different age groups. The sensory analyses were performed as per the method stated by Theagarajan *et al.* (2019). All the samples for sensory were encoded and arranged in a randomized order. All samples were served in triplicates. Drinking water and crackers were served to the panelists to cleanse their palate and avoid carryover of flavor, respectively. For yam slices, the sensory analysis was conducted on a 5-point hedonic scale (5 represents 'like extremely' to 1 represents 'dislike extremely'). The attributes for testing of yam slices were appearance, color, texture, itchiness, and taste. For cookies, a 9-point hedonic scale (9 represents 'like extremely' to 1 represents 'dislike extremely') was employed for attributes of appearance, color, flavor, mouthfeel, [tolerability of itching](#), taste, and aftertaste. The yam cookies most preferred by the sensory panel was denoted as the 'optimized cookie'.

Physicochemical properties of cookies

Both control and optimized yam cookies were examined for their physical properties such as weight, diameter, and thickness (width). Diameter and thickness were measured using a vernier caliper. Proximate analysis was also performed for both sample and control cookies by the AOAC method (AOAC 2016). The water activity of the cookies was assessed by the water activity meter that measures the free water molecules contained in the cookie, a critical parameter of shelf stability. The minerals content in control and optimized cookies were estimated by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) according to the method of Horwitz and Latimer (2000). Also, for both the sets, analysis of peroxide value, texture profile, and color analyses (Hunter Lab colorimeter, D25 optical sensor, Hunter Associates Laboratory, Reston, VA) were carried out to assess the effect of incorporation of yam powder

in cookies. These said values along with moisture content were checked at 10 days' interval for 100 days to assess the shelf life of the cookies.

Peroxide value

To estimate the peroxide value of the cookies, fat from the cookies was extracted using the Soxhlet apparatus by adopting the method of Lavanya *et al.* (2019). The result was expressed as mEq O₂/kg fat (Eq. 1).

$$\text{Peroxide value (PV)} = \frac{\text{Abs}}{55.84 \times w} \times \frac{1}{b} (\text{mEqO}_2/\text{kg fat}) \quad (1)$$

Where, Abs = absorbance, w = weight of fat, 55.84 = atomic weight of Fe (III), b = the slope of the Fe (III) calibration curve.

Texture profile analysis

With the help of texture analysis hardness and fracturability of cookies were evaluated by the texture analyzer (TA-XT2i; Stable Micro System, Godalming, UK). Two-point bend probe was used to estimate the texture of the cookies according to the method reported by Theagarajan *et al.* (2019).

Statistical analyses

All the experiments were performed in triplicate, and the data were expressed as mean ± SD of three independent experiments. The samples were statistically analyzed by the paired t-test using SPSS Statistics (ver. 25; IBM, USA) and *p*-value < 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results and Discussion

Optimization of the pretreatment

From the visual observation of the dried yam slices, methods 5 and 6 were found to cause less discoloration of the yam compared to the control one (Fig 1a-g). According to the sensory panel, the yam slices obtained from method 6 (combination of potassium metabisulfite, tartaric acid, and citric acid) were the nearest match to that of the control in terms of appearance, color, and texture (Fig. 1h). Both bitterness in taste and itchiness caused by yam was reduced in all treated samples; however, the maximum reduction was observed in method 6. Accordingly, the sensory panel preferred it the most. Apart from method 6, method 5 (combination of potassium metabisulfite and tartaric acid) was also liked by the sensory panel, especially in terms of taste. However, the reduction of itchiness was higher in method 4 (combination of

potassium metabisulfite and citric acid) compared to method 5, as opined in the panel report. Based on aggregate scores, method 6 was selected as the optimized method of pretreatment to reduce the inherent bitterness and itchiness in yam tubers. Table S1 (supplementary file) displays the difference in characteristics of both control and treated yam powders.

Phytochemical properties

Total phenolic content

The total phenolic content of the treated yam powder was 0.438 ± 0.023 g gallic acid equivalents/g sample, which was significantly higher than the values obtained for control yam powder (0.266 ± 0.23 g gallic acid equivalents/g sample). The increase in the value of phenols could result from the pretreatment techniques; similar results were also obtained by Singh, Chaurasiya, and Mitra (2020) who reported an enhanced total phenolic content of elephant foot yam cubes processed with 2% salt solution; also, Managa *et al.* (2019) observed increased antioxidant and total phenolic content of Chinese cabbage (*Brassica rapa* L. subsp. *chinensis*) blanched with 5% lemon juice.

Saponin content

The saponin content of control yam powder was found to be $1.65\pm 0.002\%$, whereas, after treatment ($0.86\pm 0.001\%$) i.e., it reduced to almost half of the initial value. Previous researchers have found the saponin content in white yam to be 2.71% (Ojokoh & Adeleke, 2020). The difference in the values may be due to the variation in the variety of yam. The pretreatment method optimized in this study proves the reduction of the saponin in water yam. The reduction by hot water blanching has also been observed by Indriasari, Kumalaningsih, and others (2016) in moringa leaves and Nigerian vegetables by Temitope, Salau, and Adewale (2013). Indriasari, Kumalaningsih, and others (2016) further assert that among 75, 85, and 95°C, the best results were obtained at 85°C. The authors opined that at a high temperature of blanching, enhanced osmosis occurs due to softened tissues, and saponins then decrease.

Optimization of the concentration of yam powder in cookies

Fig. 2 displays the control and yam cookies (with treated powder) prepared in this study. The sensory analysis of all the cookies revealed that yam cookies except the cookie prepared with 15% yam, did not show irritation for the sensory panelists (Fig. 3). The control cookie scored low in taste and mouthfeel compared to most of the yam cookies owing to a bland taste; also,

the sensory panel was not satisfied with the 1% yam cookie for a similar reason. It was observed that with an increase in concentration (up to 13%) of yam powder, the sensory acceptance of cookies increased. Cookie prepared with 15% yam powder caused mild irritation in the throat to most of the panelists, and they also disliked the bitterness and the dark brown color of these cookies. Overall from the sensory results, it was evident that cookies with 13% treated yam powder showed the highest acceptability (Fig. 3).

Physicochemical properties of the yam cookies

The physical parameters (weight, diameter, and thickness) of both control and optimized yam cookies were found to be similar (Table 2). Proximate analysis of the cookies revealed a significant difference between control and optimized cookies; the crude fiber and ash content of yam cookies were significantly higher compared to control (Table 2). These indicate incorporation of yam enhanced the nutritional properties of the cookies.

The water activity of the yam cookie was found to be lesser (0.30 ± 0.02) than that of the control cookie (0.37 ± 0.02) which facilitated the shelf life of the yam cookie. With yam powder as the ingredient, yam cookies exhibited significantly higher mineral contents compared to control cookies that improved the functional properties of treated cookies (Table 2).

Shelf life study of cookies

Moisture content

During the shelf-life study of the cookies, initially, a sharp increase in the moisture content of the control cookie was observed till 30 days; whereas, a gradual increase was detected in the optimized yam cookies till 60 days of storage that helped in maintaining the texture profile of the same during storage. After that, however, an insignificant increase in the moisture content was noted in both the cookies (Fig. 4a). The fast absorption of moisture by control cookies led to deterioration in the texture profile of the cookies (Fig. 4 c,d).

Peroxide value

Peroxide value relates to the degree of rancidity in the cookies on storing. From the result obtained it was evident that after a month of storage, the increase of peroxide value in the control cookie was higher compared to that of yam cookie (Fig. 4b). This exhibits the inherent antioxidant property of yam powder, and the antioxidants administered during pretreatment. At the end of the storage study (100 days), the peroxide value of yam cookie was 4.6 ± 0.1

mEq.O₂/kg fat that was lower than the control cookies. Therefore, optimized yam cookies can be stored for a longer period than the control cookie.

Texture profile

Texture profile analysis exhibited a gradual increase in fracturability and a decrease in hardness for control and yam cookies. However, deterioration in the texture profile with storage was significantly higher in control cookies than yam cookie (Fig 4c,d). The hardness of yam cookies (2362.792±280.83 g) was found to be significantly higher compared to control cookies (1899.13±127.07 g), possibly due to the less moisture content in yam cookies. Also, the replacement of refined wheat flour by yam powder could have improved the texture and hardness of the cookies.

Color analysis

From the color analysis data, the brightness of the yam cookie was found to be significantly higher than the control cookie, owing to the incorporation of bright yellow treated yam powder (Fig. 4e). But, there was an insignificant change of color values with storage in all cookies.

Conclusions

Water yam has several health benefits; however, due to the bitterness and irritation in the throat caused by its saponin, its commercial food application is hampered. In the current study, among different pretreatments, the process involving blanching (at 80°C for 10 min) with 0.2% potassium metabisulfite, 0.5% tartaric acid, and 0.5% citric acid was selected as the best method for pretreating the yam slices. This find was attested by the sensory panel. It was found that the said pretreatment reduces saponin content in yam by almost 50%. The yam powder (13%) incorporated cookies showed enhanced fiber, and mineral content along with higher shelf stability compared to control cookies. The addition of yam powder in cookies improved the texture, color, and most importantly acceptability of cookies by the sensory panel. This study lays a fundamental technique in exploring the benefits of yam flour being utilized in the commercial food system.

Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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Figure

Figure 1 Dried water yam slices after different pretreatment methods and the sensory analysis of the same, a) control, b) method 1, c) method 2, d) method 3, e) method 4, f) method 5, g) method 6, h) sensory analyses of yam powders

Figure 2 Cookies prepared with different concentrations of treated yam powder.

Figure 3 Sensory analyses of control and different yam cookies.

Figure 4 Physicochemical analysis conducted during shelf-life study of control and optimized yam cookies, a) moisture content, b) peroxide value, c) fracturability study, d) hardness and e) color analysis.

Table 1 Different blanching techniques used in this study

Pretreatment no.	Compounds used for blanching	Process
Control	No additive	No blanching, dried at 60°C for overnight
Method 1	0.2% Potassium metabisulfite	Blanched at 80°C for 10 min and dried at 60°C for overnight
Method 2	0.2% Potassium metabisulfite	Blanched at 80°C for 10 min followed by steeping for 10 min and dried at 60°C for overnight
Method 3	0.2% Potassium metabisulfite and 2% calcium chloride	Blanched at 80°C for 10 min and dried at 60°C for overnight
Method 4	0.2% Potassium metabisulfite and 0.5% citric acid	Blanched at 80°C for 10 min and dried at 60°C for overnight
Method 5	0.2% Potassium metabisulfite and 0.5% tartaric acid	Blanched at 80°C for 10 min and dried at 60°C for overnight
Method 6	0.2% Potassium metabisulfite, 0.5% tartaric acid and 0.5% citric acid	Blanched at 80°C for 10 min and dried at 60°C for overnight

Table 2 Physicochemical properties (wet basis) of control and yam cookies.

Components		Control cookie	Optimized yam cookie
Weight (g)		3.73±0.10 ^a	4.46±0.10 ^a
Diameter (mm)		40.68±0.58 ^a	40.87±0.9 ^a
Thickness (mm)		4.74±0.10 ^a	4.70±0.10 ^a
Water activity (a_w)		0.37 ±0.02 ^a	0.30±0.02 ^b
Moisture (%)		3.10±0.02 ^a	3.05±0.01 ^a
Protein (%)		8.40±0.62 ^a	8.31±0.86 ^a
Fat (%)		12.80±1.01 ^b	12.20±0.21 ^a
Ash (%)		1.19±0.01 ^a	1.65±0.30 ^b
Crude fiber (%)		0.50±0.02 ^a	1.10±0.01 ^b
Carbohydrate (%)		74.01±0.02 ^b	73.69±0.03 ^a
Mineral content (mg/100 g)	Phosphorous	86.72±0.82 ^b	116.20±0.80 ^a
	Potassium	110.50±0.90 ^b	221.11±0.98 ^a

Different alphabets in a row represent a significant difference at $p \leq 0.05$